
Research

Challenges in Developing Disruptive Innovation in Start-ups in Nigeria

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Abstract: This study addresses the underexplored realm of disruptive innovation within the rising economies of Africa, with a specific focus on Nigeria. While disruptive innovation is extensively studied in advanced economies, this research sheds light on the challenges faced by Nigerian start-ups aspiring to achieve disruptive innovation. The analysis highlights the entrepreneurial environment, emphasizing the hurdles such as energy supply shortages, limited investment opportunities, and inadequate government policies. Leveraging primary and secondary data, the study identifies opportunities for disruptive innovation in Nigeria across various industries. Strategies for overcoming challenges are discussed, including the use of mobile technology, support from governmental and educational entities, and targeting underserved markets. The research concludes that disruptive innovation is vital for the survival and competitiveness of Nigerian start-ups. The findings are valuable for stakeholders such as business owners, decision-makers, and investors, offering practical insights into navigating the complex landscape of disruptive innovation in a developing economy like Nigeria. Despite challenges, the study asserts that with the right resources and innovation, Nigerian start-ups can drive transformative solutions, fostering industry growth and development.

Keywords: disruptive innovation, start-ups, disruptive strategies, business model innovation, disruptive innovation in a developing economy.

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Introduction

In the world of organizational dynamics, innovation emerges as a key driver for competitive advantage and economic growth. Noteworthy scholars such as Garcia & Calantone (2002), and Neely et al. (2002), and others highlight the dual nature of innovation—through process and product innovation, often interwoven. Despite considerable investments,

innovations often fall short, leading to the development of diverse models by thought leaders like Magnusson et al., (2003), Norman and Verganti, (2012), Veryzer (1998), Teece (1986), and Radjou et al., (2012).

However, overreliance on established frameworks may hinder product evolution, a concern raised by Utterback, 1994; Christensen, 1997. The support and development of developing countries over the past years have depended on their ability to innovate (Damanpour & Wischnevsky, 2006; Nagano et al., 2014) particularly for developing nations like Nigeria. Acknowledging Nigeria's burgeoning start-up ecosystem with its challenges—outlined by Adewale et al., (2013). This concurs with a recent study by Christensen et al. (2018) that urges more investigation into the specifics of disruption processes (Si & Chen, 2020; Zhang and al., 2020) that also called for more research in developing economies. Despite obstacles, Nigerian start-ups possess transformative potential, necessitating sufficient support. By exploring barriers, analyzing the start-up environment, and using diverse data sources, the research aims to offer unique insights such as strategies for success, the role of government support exploring regulatory, financial, technological, and market-related obstacles and proposing solutions to foster a conducive environment for disruptive innovation.

Literature Review

Introduction to disruptive innovation

The landscape of disruptive innovation is rapidly evolving, and while much attention has been given to advanced economies, this study aims to analyse the underexplored realm within the rising economies of Africa, with a specific attention on Nigeria. In a country marked by a burgeoning start-up ecosystem, the research delves into the challenges faced by Nigerian start-ups aspiring to achieve disruptive innovation and offers valuable insights for stakeholders.

Disruptive innovation, per Christensen (1997), is when a product becomes competitive in prices and now more accessible after an initial poor performance in the mainstream market. Originally termed "disruptive technology," it described lower-grade technologies (Christensen & Raynor, 2003; Kirzner, 1973). Despite this, the results of this fundamental research are still applicable today, and other authors have helped to advance this theory. Markides (2006) differentiates disruptive technology, goods, and business model innovation, while Christensen et al. (2004) demonstrate how government regulations impact industry innovation. In the realm of start-ups, Christensen (1997) highlights their potential to challenge market leaders. Successful disruptive innovation, as outlined by Sopjani (2019), offers a competitive advantage, attracting customers and disrupting established players.

Transitioning to the context of start-ups, the adoption of disruptive innovation involves a strategic blend of creativity, risk-taking, and an entrepreneurial mindset, as highlighted by Christensen (1997). This approach allows start-ups not only to challenge established businesses but also to capitalize on untapped markets, particularly by concentrating on low-end clients and emerging markets. Successful execution of disruptive innovation strategies, as observed by Sopjani (2019) empowers start-ups with a competitive advantage, attracting customers, mitigating technological risks, and requiring lower start-up finances. This underscores the pivotal role of disruptive innovation in reshaping industries and fostering the growth of emerging businesses.

In the realm of disruptive innovation, scholars, including Christensen et al. (2002) note a gap in tools and frameworks for identifying disruptive potential at the outset, emphasizing the need for first response data. The distinction between sustaining and disruptive innovation lies in the performance improvement aspect, with sustaining innovations targeting mainstream customers (Govindarajan and Kopalle, 2006b). Recent trends in disruptive innovation literature, highlighted by Bruton et al. (2013), underscore a growing focus on lean start-up methodologies, management techniques,

and the role of venture capital, both domestically and internationally. The theoretical framework surrounding disruptive innovation has expanded over the last two decades, addressing questions of definition refinement, strategies for mitigation, and efforts to spot disruptive products at early market stages (Christensen et al., 2015).

Disruptive innovation in start-ups

Birch in 1979 defined start-ups as crucial engines for innovation, while Blank in 2011 characterizes them as provisional businesses with scalable models, especially prevalent in tech. The discussion covers start-up development phases, addressing challenges like funding and governmental constraints. Inspired by Clayton Christensen, the theory of disruptive start-ups posits that they initially target niche markets but can grow to challenge established companies (Christensen, 1997). There is a need for vigilance in established companies and highlights opportunities disruptive start-ups offer for entrepreneurs and investors (Markman & Waldron, 2014; Coeurderoy & Murray, 2014). Start-ups employ disruptive strategies, facing challenges like limited resources, economic uncertainties, and technological shifts, requiring innovative approaches for survival (Christensen & Raynor, 2003). Disruptive innovation influences metrics such as technological features, market dynamics, and the external environment, impacting SMEs' performance and global competition (Ayodele et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2022). Additionally, business model innovation, defined as creating innovative revenue-generating methods, value delivery, and operational enhancement, plays a vital role in market dominance for start-ups (Magretta, 2002), allowing for competitive pricing and appealing earnings. Amidst the pursuit of business growth, companies, both start-ups and established firms, leverage innovative business models as a strategic tool to reimagine fundamental operations, gain a competitive edge, adapt to evolving markets, and create new opportunities; notable examples include subscription-based, sharing economy, and freemium models that disrupt traditional industries.

Disruptive innovation in developing economies (Focus on Nigeria)

Disruptive innovation in developing economies is often overlooked in research as more attention is being paid on developed countries. This is because they hold significance for economic growth and entrepreneurship (Si et al., 2020). Researchers like Christensen advocate for studying disruptive innovation in unexplored areas, emphasizing its potential to address challenges in basic services, infrastructure, education, and literacy indicators. In developing countries like Nigeria, where SMEs and start-ups play a crucial role, disruptive innovation is pivotal for sustained growth (Mytelka & Farinelli, 2000; Wong et al., 2005; Longenecker et al., 2006). The current entrepreneurial landscape in Nigeria reflects a surge in start-ups, particularly in sectors like fintech, health, insurance, and education (Disrupt Africa). However, challenges such as access to venture capital and inconsistent government actions impact start-up success, underscoring the need for continued research and supportive ecosystems in developing economies (Osemeke, 2012; Tende, 2014; Adenle, 2017).

Nigeria, a federal country in West Africa, boasts a population of approximately 230 million citizens spread across 37 states. The entrepreneurship scene in Nigeria is fueled by disruptive innovation, with family-owned businesses prevailing and youth-led start-ups addressing unemployment (Mytelka & Farinelli, 2000; Wong et al., 2005; Longenecker et al., 2006; Onuoha, 2012; Yinusa. O, 2013). Technology propels start-ups into MSMEs dominating local markets, yet accessing venture capital remains a hurdle (Yinusa. O, 2013; Arshad et al., 2014; Coen et al., 2014; Lechner & Gudmundsson, 2012). Disruptive innovation transforms industries like healthcare, banking, agriculture, and transportation, with Nigeria boasting over 3000 start-ups, led predominantly by fintech (Akosile, 2017; Disrupt Africa).

Nigerian businesses constitute 28.4% of all funded businesses in Africa, with 29.3% of total investments on the continent directed to Nigeria. Despite a general decrease in investment activity, particularly in venture financing, businesses in Nigeria raised record amounts of funding (Guardian, 2022). Lagos serves as the economic hub, housing a majority of the nation's start-ups. Despite facing challenges such as limited access to capital and poor infrastructure, the government has initiated measures to support the start-up ecosystem, including the establishment of the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission and a \$20 million technology fund. Success stories like Paystack and Andela underscore Nigeria's potential in the global market.

Nigerian tech startups by sub-sector

Diagram 1: Nigeria's tech start-up sector, Source disrupt Africa 2022

Existing literature Gaps on disruptive innovation

The existing literature on disruptive innovation reveals several critical gaps that warrant further investigation. Critics have challenged the essential legitimacy and generalizability of Christensen's disruptive innovation theory, prompting revisions and adjustments by various authors (King & Baartartogtokh, 2015; Danneels, 2004; Nagy et al., 2016). Key gaps include the need for a clear and consistent definition of disruptive innovation, as diverse interpretations hinder comparative analysis and synthesis of findings (Nagy et al., 2016). Empirical research on disruptive innovation in start-ups within developing economies, external factors influencing disruption, and the role of human factors remains limited, calling for broader exploration (Si et al., 2020; Tellis, 2006). Additional gaps encompass contextual variations, long-term impacts, disruptive business models, and ecosystem dynamics, requiring in-depth investigations for a more comprehensive understanding of disruptive innovation (Christensen, 2015; Yu & Hang, 2010). Future research should address these gaps through rigorous empirical studies, comparative analyses, and the development of new theoretical frameworks.

Research Methodology

This qualitative study delves into the challenges faced by Nigerian start-ups in developing disruptive innovations within their socio-economic, cultural, and regulatory contexts. Utilizing interviews, observations, and document analysis, data was collected from 15 selected start-ups out of a population of 30. The sampling frame was established using various online platforms, including Naibacsocialnetwork.com, Connectnigeria.com, Startupranking.com, Angellist directory, Smileandmobile.com, Techcrunch.com, Techpoint.ng, and Nigeria.startups-list.com.

Cities	Number of start-ups
a. Enugu	4
b. Awka	4
c. Abuja	3
d. Onitsha	4
Total sample size	15

Table 1: Sample size of the various start-ups used for the study

Economic environment	Socio-cultural environment	Political environment	Global environment	Demographic environment
Access to Funding: Start-ups can obtain government funding, angel investors, and venture capital.	Entrepreneurial Culture: Social attitudes toward taking risks, failing, and starting a business.	Support from the government includes funding for innovation hubs, policies that encourage entrepreneurship, and assistance with research and development.	Access to technology includes having access to digital infrastructure, cutting-edge technology, and international marketplaces.	The percentage of the youth population that possesses creative ideas and aspires to become an entrepreneur.
Market dynamics include consumer spending power, the size of the market, and the need for new products and services.	Training and Education: Accessibility to high-quality programs for training and education in innovation and entrepreneurship.	Governance and Stability: Upholding the rule of law, safeguarding intellectual property rights, and maintaining political stability.	Competition: Existing businesses and new ventures, as well as domestic and foreign competitors.	Urbanization is the concentration of innovation hubs and start-ups in areas of cities where talent and resources are available.
Regulatory Framework: Government regulations that encourage innovation, tax breaks for new businesses, and ease of doing business.	Social Networks: The availability of networks that offer assistance, such as mentorship programs, accelerators, and start-up incubators.	Bureaucratic Obstacles: Simplicity in navigating licensing, registration, and regulatory systems.	Trade Deals: Taking part in global partnerships and trade agreements that promote innovation and information sharing.	Diversity and Inclusion: The incorporation of a range of viewpoints, experiences, and histories within the start-up community.

Table 2: The entrepreneurial environment components of disruptive innovation of new start-ups in Nigeria

Sector	Respondents	Interviewed	Responded via survey	For the anonymity of respondents
Information Technology	3	✓	0	Respondent 1
Education	2	✓	0	Respondent 2
Finance	2	✓	0	Respondent 3
Agriculture	2	✓	0	Respondent 4
Health	1	✓	0	Respondent 5
E-commerce and retail	3	✓	0	Respondent 6
Others	2	✓	0	
Total	15			

Table 3: Groups of respondents according to sectors

Data Analysis

The paper employs inductive reasoning and qualitative content analysis to analyze interview data with an open mind (Bengtsson, 2016; Krippendorff, 2018; Stemler, 2000). It involves decontextualization, recontextualization, categorization, interpretation, and drawing conclusions, ensuring objectivity and validity (Saldaa, 2015; Erlingsson & Brysiewicz, 2017). The process entails careful examination of transcribed interviews, creation of codes, and seeking verification from participants to enhance rigor (Erlingsson & Brysiewicz, 2017).

Meaningful parts	Summarized meaning	Codes	Categories	Themes
My lack of access to adequate funding and it is a major hindrance to develop disruptive innovations.	Lack of financial aid is the cause of little disruption	Challenges faced	Lack of finance	Financial constraints
Entrepreneur’s face challenges related like electricity to inadequate infrastructure, including unreliable power supply, limited internet connectivity.	Lack of supportive infrastructure	Challenges faced	Inadequate infrastructure	Lack of social amenities

<p>Emphasizing entrepreneurship education and skills development programs can equip aspiring entrepreneurs with the necessary knowledge and skills to drive disruptive innovations.</p>	<p>Entrepreneurship education and skills development</p>	<p>Obstacles to technological innovation</p>	<p>Government policies on educational institutions specialized in entrepreneurship and innovation</p>	<p>Government rednecks</p>
<p>Facilitating collaboration and networking opportunities among start-ups, industry players, academia, and research institutions foster knowledge exchange, partnerships, and innovation</p>	<p>Collaboration and Networking</p>	<p>Benefits of technological innovation and entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Government action</p>	<p>Government provision of facilities to ease collaboration in the entrepreneurship sector</p>
<p>Implementing policies and regulations that promote innovation and ease the burdensome bureaucratic processes are essential.</p>	<p>Supportive Policies and Regulations</p>	<p>Barriers to Growth of start-ups</p>	<p>Government actions should implement effective policies</p>	<p>Government policies to help start-ups develop</p>
<p>The Nigerian government can create a conducive environment for entrepreneurship. This includes formulating policies and regulations That support start-ups.</p>	<p>Government Support</p>	<p>Advantage of good government policies</p>	<p>Impact of effective and efficient policies and regulations</p>	<p>Positive influence on business</p>

Table 4: Example of Data Analysis according to (Bengtsson, 2016)

The majority of start-up owners in Nigeria possess formal education, with many holding at least a Bachelor's degree in various fields. These entrepreneurs exhibit a high level of literacy, essential for leveraging technology in their ventures, as noted by Mbuyisa and Leonard (2015b). The literacy rate in Nigeria stands at 59.57%, emphasizing the significance of education for entrepreneurial success.

In 2022, Nigeria saw an increase in start-up creation, exceeding 3,360, with the trend continuing upwards. Most start-ups, particularly SMEs, have emerged within the past five years, utilizing technology as their primary tool for innovation and economic development. However, there has been a decline in start-up launches from 2019 to 2023, with Lagos remaining a focal point for entrepreneurial activities.

Challenges faced by start-ups	Number of respondents	Percentages
Access to finance	15	100%
Lack of infrastructures	15	100%
Poor connectivity and digital advancement	8	53%
Lack of formal education and training	7	46%
Intense competition due to small market and opportunities	8	53%
Political unpredictability and undefined government policies	12	80%
Others	7	46%

Table 5: Challenges faced by start-ups in their quest to achieve Disruptive Innovation

Research Findings

The research findings provide a comprehensive analysis of the challenges faced by Nigerian start-ups in developing disruptive innovations. These challenges are multifaceted and deeply rooted in the socio-economic and regulatory landscape of Nigeria. By delving into the specific obstacles encountered by start-ups, such as limited access to funding, a shortage of skilled talent, difficulties in technology adoption, high competition, expensive internet connectivity, challenges in obtaining loans, limited market access, and inadequate infrastructure, the study offers a nuanced understanding of the complexities involved in fostering disruptive innovation. The research reveals that start-ups in Nigeria face significant challenges such as insufficient funding, inadequate infrastructure, and burdensome governmental regulations. These obstacles hinder their survival and impede their capacity to drive revolutionary innovation.

Causes and Challenges in Nigeria's Entrepreneurial Environment for Disruptive Innovation

Limited access to finance emerges as the primary challenge hindering start-ups from achieving disruptive innovation, as highlighted by 100% of respondents. Financial constraints not only jeopardize the survival of start-ups but also impede their ability to invest in innovation, as entrepreneurs prioritize survival over innovation.

Infrastructure deficiencies also pose significant barriers to start-up sustainability and innovation. Around 80% of respondents cite government bottlenecks and an unfavourable business environment as obstacles to growth through technological advancements. Lack of reliable energy, efficient transportation systems, and modern communication networks further hinder SMEs' progress, echoing findings by Mohammed Sani (2017).

Complex regulatory frameworks and bureaucratic processes make it difficult for start-ups to navigate legal requirements and obtain necessary permits or licenses. This can hinder the development and implementation of disruptive innovations.

There is a shortage of skilled talent with the expertise needed to drive disruptive innovation in Nigeria. Brain drain and insufficient investment in education and skills development exacerbate this talent gap, limiting start-ups' ability to attract and retain top talent.

Nigeria's diverse market landscape, characterized by varying consumer preferences, cultural norms, and economic disparities, presents challenges for start-ups seeking to introduce disruptive innovations. Adapting innovations to suit different market segments requires significant resources and market insights.

The lack of investment in research and development infrastructure and initiatives stifles innovation in Nigeria. Without adequate R&D support, start-ups struggle to develop and commercialize disruptive technologies.

The study underlines the critical role of education, access to finance, and infrastructure in fostering innovation and entrepreneurial success in Nigeria's start-up ecosystem. Addressing these challenges is crucial for unleashing the full potential of Nigerian entrepreneurs and driving economic growth.

Results and Discussion

The Nigerian Government's Policies and Initiatives to Help Start-ups

Innovation is key to boosting productivity in SMEs and start-ups and integrating global markets. According to OECD (2019), digitalisation has presented an effective instrument to reduce the size disadvantage of SMEs. This is the reason why the Nigerian government has adopted several policies to facilitate disruptive innovation in the country as they have understood that innovation and entrepreneurship play a vital role in the development of the nation. One of the key initiatives is the establishment of research grants and funding opportunities for scientists and innovators to pursue their projects and contribute to the nation's development.

Furthermore, the government has also fostered partnerships between academia, industry, and government agencies to facilitate knowledge transfer, technology commercialization, and the development of innovative solutions to address the country's challenges. These collaborations aim to harness the potential of science, technology, and innovation to drive economic growth, improve healthcare delivery, and enhance national security.

In addition, the government has prioritized the development of STEM education and skills training to build a strong workforce capable of driving technological advancements and innovation in various sectors. By investing in human capital and infrastructure, the government is laying the foundation for sustainable development and long-term competitiveness in the global economy. Some examples of government initiatives include: The Technology Incubation Program (TIP), The Venture Capital Trust Fund (VCTF) and The Presidential Enabling Business Environment Council (PEBEC).

Several universities and organizations have established incubation centres to provide support to start-ups. These centres provide access to funding, mentorship, training, and networking opportunities. Mavuri et al. (2023) conducted research and found out that the incubates were not very happy with the services obtained from these Centres and called for better management to optimize its services.

The government has established several funding schemes to support start-ups. These funding schemes include the Central Bank of Nigeria's Creative Industry Financing Initiative (CIFI), the Bank of Industry (BOI) Youth Entrepreneurship Support (YES) program, and the Tony Elumelu Foundation Entrepreneurship Programme (Nigerian Start-up Act 2022).

The government provides tax incentives to start-ups to encourage innovation. These tax incentives include tax holidays and exemptions from certain taxes.

The Nigerian government has established laws and institutions to protect intellectual property. The Nigerian Copyright Commission and the Nigerian Patent and Trademark Office are responsible for the protection of intellectual property in Nigeria (Nigerian Start-up Act 2022).

Technology hubs have been established in Nigeria to provide start-ups with access to resources and networking opportunities. Some of these hubs include the CoCreation Hub (CCHub), Ventures Platform, and the Wennovation Hub (Nigerian Start-up Act 2022). These policies and programs have helped to ease the challenges faced by disruptive innovation start-ups in Nigeria. However, there is still room for improvement, and more needs to be done to support the growth and development of start-ups in Nigeria.

Policy Suggestions for Startup Ecosystem Development: Government and Enterprise Perspectives

In the course of this research, many respondents made some policy recommendations to help start-ups develop. These policy suggestions aim to create an enabling environment for disruptive innovation in Nigeria and provide support for start-ups and small businesses.

Government Perspective

1. **Create an Enabling Regulatory Environment:** The government should streamline regulatory processes and create clear and transparent regulatory frameworks that support innovation and entrepreneurship. This includes simplifying business registration procedures, reducing bureaucratic red tape, and providing incentives for startups.
2. **Increase Access to Funding:** Implement policies to facilitate access to financing for startups, including venture capital funds, angel investors, and government-backed grants or loans. Establish dedicated funds or investment programs to support disruptive innovation initiatives.
3. **Foster Collaboration and Partnerships:** Encourage collaboration between government agencies, research institutions, and the private sector to promote innovation ecosystems. This could involve creating innovation hubs, technology parks, and incubators to facilitate knowledge sharing and networking among startups.
4. **Invest in Infrastructure Development:** Prioritize infrastructure development, including improving access to reliable electricity, high-speed internet, and transportation networks. Enhancing infrastructure will create a conducive environment for startups to develop and scale disruptive innovations.
5. **Support Education and Skills Development:** Invest in education and skills development programs to nurture a talent pool equipped with the skills needed for disruptive innovation. This includes promoting STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education, entrepreneurship training, and vocational programs.

Enterprise Perspective

1. **Focus on Research and Development (R&D):** Prioritize investment in R&D activities to drive innovation and develop disruptive technologies. Allocate resources to explore new ideas, experiment with novel approaches, and create innovative solutions that address market needs.
2. **Build Strategic Partnerships:** Collaborate with other startups, industry players, research institutions, and government agencies to leverage complementary expertise, resources, and networks. Strategic partnerships can facilitate access to new markets, technologies, and funding opportunities.
3. **Invest in Talent Development:** Prioritize talent development initiatives to attract, retain, and develop skilled professionals capable of driving disruptive innovation. Offer training programs, mentorship opportunities, and career development pathways to nurture a highly skilled workforce.

4. **Embrace Agile and Iterative Approaches:** Adopt agile methodologies and iterative processes to rapidly prototype, test, and iterate on innovative ideas. Emphasize flexibility, adaptability, and continuous learning to respond to market feedback and evolving customer needs.
5. **Advocate for Supportive Policies:** Engage with policymakers and industry associations to advocate for policies that support innovation and entrepreneurship. Provide input on regulatory reforms, funding initiatives, and infrastructure development plans to create a favourable operating environment for startups.

By implementing these policy suggestions from both the government and enterprise perspectives, Nigeria can foster a vibrant ecosystem for disruptive innovation, driving economic growth, job creation, and sustainable development.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research findings highlight the myriad challenges that disruptive innovation start-ups face in Nigeria, ranging from limited access to funding and technology to intense competition and regulatory hurdles. These obstacles significantly impede the growth and success of start-ups striving to achieve disruptive innovation in the Nigerian entrepreneurial landscape.

Access to finance emerges as a critical challenge, with many entrepreneurs struggling to secure adequate funding to develop and scale their disruptive ideas. This is compounded by a lack of technology infrastructure and skilled talent, further hindering the ability of start-ups to innovate and compete effectively in the market. Moreover, the highly competitive nature of Nigeria's market, coupled with bureaucratic inefficiencies and limited market access, presents significant barriers to entry for disruptive innovation start-ups.

However, despite these challenges, there are strategies and approaches that start-ups can employ to overcome these obstacles. Innovation and creativity, collaboration and networking, strategic planning, access to funding, and government support are identified as key avenues through which start-ups can navigate the complexities of the Nigerian business environment and foster disruptive innovation.

Furthermore, government policies and initiatives play a crucial role in supporting the growth and development of disruptive innovation start-ups in Nigeria. Policies such as the National Science, Technology, and Innovation Roadmap, the National Innovation and Entrepreneurship Strategy, and initiatives like the Technology Incubation Program and the Venture Capital Trust Fund are aimed at creating an enabling environment for innovation and entrepreneurship. Additionally, incubation centers, funding opportunities, tax incentives, intellectual property protection, and technology hubs provide vital support structures for start-ups to thrive.

In light of these findings, it is evident that concerted efforts from policymakers, stakeholders, and entrepreneurs are essential to address the challenges and leverage the opportunities inherent in Nigeria's entrepreneurial landscape. By fostering a supportive ecosystem for disruptive innovation, Nigeria can unlock its potential as a hub for transformative change, driving economic growth, technological advancement, and social progress for its citizens.

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